

This dataset concerns the paper :

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From tissues to segmentation: a modular framework for multi-scale neuron isolation

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Original paper can be found on Nature Communication website :

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-024-48146-y>

Table of content of Image Dataset

We provided here the raw dataset concerning purkinje cells from Figure 1,2, 3 & 6 and rat hippocampal Pyramidal cell of Figure 7 and Supplementary Figure 18 & 19.

You will find:

- Mice Purkinje cell in tissue slice (Figure 1, 6 from Inserm): **10.5281/zenodo.10806305**

Figure 1M is a region of Interest provided in file « PurkinjeCells 20x Confocal.tif ».

Figure 1N & O is coming from « PurkinjeCells 93x confocal-ZProjection.tif » which is a Z projection of the raw data « PurkinjeCells 93x confocal.tif » which contains 204 Z slices.

Figure 1P is provided in « PurkinjeCells 93x STED.tif ».

- Mice Purkinje cell in tissue slice (Figure 3 from Pisa): **10.5281/zenodo.10806305**

- Rat hippocampal pyramidal cell in culture (Figure 7, Figure Sup 18 and 19 from Insemm): DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.10936111](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10936111)

SENPAI

SENPAI is an automated tool implemented in Matlab (The MathWorks-Inc., United States) and released as a freely available toolbox at: <https://github.com/cauzzo-s5/SENPAI>. It can be used to reconstruct neuronal morphology, from spine detection and morphometry up to whole neuron arborization, starting from 3D optical images from any type of microscope including confocal, multiphoton, STED, etc. It implements two fundamental steps: a segmentation step and a parcellation step.